

EFFECTS OF THERMAL HISTORIES ON CF/PA 6 MICROCOMPOSITE LOAD TRANSFER EFFICIENCY: MEASUREMENT, CRYSTALLIZATION AND MODULUS

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ABSTRACT

Load transfer efficiencies of single CF/PA 6 microcomposites with different cooling rates and annealing treatments were measured by electrical resistance method. POM and XRD were used to observe crystal morphologies and characterize crystal forms in their matrices and interfaces, respectively. Tensile properties of neat PA 6 with the same thermal histories were tested. Results showed that electrical resistance method was an effective way to characterize load transfer efficiency of the interface. It was also very interesting to find that water quenched microcomposites had the highest load transfer efficiency of 94.2%. Moreover, decreasing cooling rate or increasing annealing temperature or time all resulted in a higher crystallinity degree, a higher tensile strength, a larger transcrystalline region, but a lower load transfer efficiency. These results are unexpected and inconsistent with previously reported outcomes of some other thermoplastics obtained by IFSS method. This might be due to the different crystallization kinetics behaviours for these semicrystalline polymers and diverse evaluation methods.

1 INTRODUCTION

The mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced thermoplastics depend critically on the strength and modulus of fiber and matrix as well as the load transfer at the interface between fiber and matrix [1-3]. Most of these factors are basically determined by the microstructures of their compositions including crystallinity, spherulite size, and crystal forms of the matrix, transcrystallization at the interface and some other factors controlled by thermal histories during composites manufacture [4]. A great deal of studies have been performed to understand the influences of these parameters, but no apparent consensus was achieved on cooling rate [5-11] and transcrystallization [4, 5, 12-14] affecting interfacial shear strength (IFSS) or load transfer efficiency for different thermoplastic composites. These disputes probably result from the difference of fiber/polymer systems and processing conditions.

Load transfer efficiency was defined and measured by electrical resistance method because carbon fibers were in-situ or intrinsic strain sensors and typically applied to obtain relationships between electrical resistance and strain [15-18]. The load transfer efficiencies from matrix to fiber of single carbon fiber reinforced PA 6 microcomposites with different cooling rates and annealing treatments were calculated by electrical resistance change ratios according to a standard calibration curve of naked single carbon fiber.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

T700 carbon fiber, 1013B PA 6 were used to prepare load transfer efficiency measurement samples. Single fiber was connected with the copper using silver paste at the point of intersection as shown schematically in Figure 1. After the silver paste was cured, dry nylon 6 was poured into the dog-bone shaped mold cavities and then heated to 260 °C in an air-circulating oven for 10 min. Subsequently, water quenching (Water), between two aluminum plates (Al), air cooling (Air) were proceeded. Annealing specimens were obtained by immersing water-quenched microcomposites in

silicone oil at 130 °C for 5 h (Ann-130), 170 °C for 5 h (Ann-170) and 200 °C for 5 h (Ann-200), respectively.

Figure 1: Mold for prepare dogbone-shaped single carbon fiber microcomposites used for load transfer efficiency measurement by electrical resistance method

Load transfer efficiency η is defined as ratio of fiber strain ε_f in the microcomposite and applied strain on the microcomposite ε_c , as expressed in Eq. 1, and calculated through Eq. 2.

$$\eta = \frac{\varepsilon_f}{\varepsilon_c} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

$$\eta = \varepsilon_f / \varepsilon_c = (\Delta R / R_0 K_f) / (\Delta R / R_0 K_c) = (K_c / K_f) \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Where K_c and K_f illustrates as the proportionality factor of electrical resistance change ratio $\Delta R / R_0$ of the fiber versus applied strain on the microcomposite and naked fiber, respectively. More detailed information was submitted to Journal of Polymer Composites.

Crystal morphology was performed on a Leica DM4000M polarizing microscope using 50 μm thin film specimens. Crystal forms were characterized by D/max-2200 $\text{CuK}\alpha$ XRD scanning from 7.5° to 30° at a rate of 5 °/min. Tensile properties were also tested on a mechanical testing machine at rate of 0.2 mm/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Crystallization behaviours

It was found that there were two different crystallization kinetics behaviours between nonisothermal cooling and annealing treatment for CF/PA 6 composites. As can be seen in Figure 2, the annealing process tends to increase the degree of crystallinity preferentially in the form of imperfect spherulites with small lamellar structure mainly in the bulky matrix, whereas the nonisothermal cooling encourages more transcrystallization at the interface region and formation of larger and thicker but lower density spherulites induced by a decreased supercooling degree [19].

For a practical composite with a large volume fraction of fibers, the bulky matrix may predominantly have a transcrystalline morphology linking all the fibers as shown in Figure 2g. Therefore, the anisotropic transcrystalline phase may be expected to affect the properties of the composite by affecting the load transfer at the interface and the mechanical properties of the surrounding matrix region [20].

Figure 2: Polarizing optical micrographs of T700/PA 6 single fiber microcomposites with different cooling rates and annealing treatments: (a) Water, (b) Al, (c) Air, (d) Ann-130, (e) Ann-170, (f) Ann-200, (g) transcrystals between two single carbon fibers

Figure 3: XRD patterns of PA 6 with different cooling rates and annealing treatments

From the results of XRD test, quenching of the semicrystalline PA 6 and subsequent annealing

were shown to give similar results as slow cooling as shown in Figure 3. High cooling rate of water quenching leads to formation of γ -phase, as indicated by the strong 001 peak at 21.4 degree (2θ) corresponding to an interplanar spacing of 0.42 nm. The γ -phase is increasingly replaced by α -crystals with decreasing cooling rate and increasing annealing temperature, which can be recognized by the appearance of the 200 and 002/202 α peaks at 20.2 and 23.7 degree (2θ) corresponding to the interplanar distances of 0.44 and 0.38 nm, respectively. It is also worth noting that decreasing cooling rate is more inclined to the formation of smaller interplanar distance α_1 (200) crystal, while increasing annealing temperature is more in favour of α_2 (002/202) formation of larger interplanar spacing, which in detail also indicate different crystallization kinetics behaviours between nonisothermal cooling and annealing treatment for PA 6.

3.2 Tensile properties

Tensile strengths and moduli for each microcomposite with different cooling rates and annealing treatments are shown in Figure 4. It is obvious that the elastic modulus of PA 6 increases, while the ductility decreases for both decreasing cooling rate and increasing annealing temperature or time. It ascribes to the high crystallinity of crystallites obtained at a low cooling rate, a high annealing temperature or a long annealing time. It means that it is so difficult to induce slips in the crystal blocks due to higher orderliness and thicker lamellae that yielding is more difficult to take place with dramatically reduced ductility [5].

Figure 4: Representative stress-strain profiles of neat PA 6 with different cooling rates and annealing treatments

3.3 Load transfer efficiency

Figure 5a shows a good linear relationship between electrical resistance change and applied strain with an average strain sensitivity K_f of 1.66 for naked T700 single carbon fiber. As the results shown, water quenched sample have a highest load transfer efficiency of 94.2% but a lowest matrix modulus and a minimum transcrystalline region. Decreasing cooling rate or increasing annealing temperature or time all result in a higher matrix modulus, a larger transcrystalline region, but a lower load transfer efficiency with 34.3% at the bottom for 200°C annealing treatment.

Figure 5: (a) Single T700 carbon fiber strain sensitivity coefficient and (b) load transfer efficiencies of single fiber reinforced PA 6 microcomposites with different thermal treatments

With regards to the results of our experiments, transcrystallization, high matrix modulus seems have negative effects on load transfer efficiency. Interface modulus is doubtfully considered as the positive factor based on previously reported conclusions. Since it is commonly accepted and can be roughly seen in Figure 2 that the diameter of the transcrystalline phase decreases with increasing cooling rate, but the nucleation density increases due to the higher degree of supercooling (nucleation driving force) [20, 21], which may result in a higher interface modulus next to fiber surface and lead to a higher load transfer efficiency. Another parameter worth considering is residual stress. It was found that slight mechanical stress at the fibre polymer interface gave rise to surface nucleation and growth of transcrystalline regions [21]. Residual stress is often induced during manufacture of composites and still does not have a consistency in effects of cooling rate and load transfer efficiency for various polymers [22]. Further studies focused on interface like modulus, thickness, shear strength, adhesion strength and residual stress are going to be performed.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Load transfer efficiencies for T700 single carbon fiber reinforced PA 6 microcomposites with different cooling rates and annealing treatments were measured by electrical resistance method. The results show that water quenched samples had a highest load transfer efficiency of 94.2% but a lowest matrix modulus and a minimum transcrystalline region. Decreasing cooling rate or increasing annealing temperature or time all resulted in a higher matrix modulus, a larger transcrystalline region, but a lower load transfer efficiency with 34.3% at the bottom for 200°C annealing treatment. The results provide a valuable reference for composite manufacture and applications with a large volume fraction of fibers such as thermoplastic composite prepregs. There was also an inconsistency with previously reported conclusions in some other fiber reinforced thermoplastics determined by fiber fragmentation. Various crystallization kinetics behaviours for different semicrystalline polymers may be the dominant reason for this inconsistency. Further studies focused on interfacial properties like modulus, thickness, shear strength, adhesion strength and residual stress are going to be performed.

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